

Authorship, Etymology and Typification of *Cereaster* and *Terecaulis*, Two Forgotten Cactus Genera (Cactaceae)

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Abstract—The author of *Cereaster* and *Terecaulis*, two overlooked genera of Cactaceae, is not Ernst Berge, but Karl Friedrich Wilhelm Berge. For both names etymologies are proposed. It may be necessary to propose the name *Cereaster* for rejection.

In the 1842 and 1843 editions of the encyclopedia *Das Buch der Welt* [‘The Book of the World’] two new cactus genera were established: *Cereaster* for species with thin, flexible, scandent, sprawling and hanging stems that were hitherto included in *Cereus* Mill., and *Terecaulis* for *Opuntia* (L.) Mill. species with terete rather than compressed segments (Berge: 1842, 1843).

Both genera were all but overlooked by later authors, although *Cereaster grandiflorus* [*Selenicereus grandiflorus* (L.) Britton & Rose] was notably included under this name in Baenitz (1877: 69-70), a popular botany textbook. Roy Mottram briefly discussed *Terecaulis* in Crook & Mottram (1997).

Authorship—The author of the genera was named only as ‘Berge’ in both editions of *Das Buch der Welt*. Mottram identified him as Leipzig-based gardener and plant importer Ernst Berge (1836-1897)². If this identification is correct, Berge probably was the the youngest botanist in history, describing new genera at age six.

The true author was almost certainly naturalist, ornithologist and entomologist Friedrich Berge (1811-1883). His classic *Schmetterlingsbuch* [‘Butterfly

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² See also the entry for Ernst Berge in The International Plant Names Index, <https://www.ipni.org/a/13874-1> (accessed 6 August 2019). He is not to be confused with Ernst Berger, who incidentally accepted *Cereaster* sensu de Candolle (see below) as a subdivision of *Cereus* [unranked] *Eucereus* Miq. in Berger (1855: 288).

Book'] is cited in an article titled *Seltene europäische Schmetterlinge* ['Rare European Butterflies'] in the 1843 edition of *Das Buch der Welt* (pp. 8-9). Like the two cactus articles, both the butterfly article and the book are attributed only to 'Berge', indicating that they were written by the same person.

Friedrich Berge is mainly remembered for his entomological work, but in his younger years he wrote a booklet with the fanciful title *Anweisung zur zweckmäßigen Behandlung der Cactuspflanzen, um solche freudig gedeihen und schön blühen zu sehen* ['Manual for the Effective Treatment of Cactus Plants to See Them Thrive Happily and Flower Beautifully'; Stuttgart: Scheible's Buchhandlung, 1832; not seen].³ A short biography was published by Calmbach (1921).

Although Berge's full name is given als Carl Friedrich Wilhelm Berge by most modern sources, he published *Anweisung ...* as K. F. W. Berge, which suggests he preferred the spelling Karl. In later books he called himself F. Berge or Fr. Berge. In accordance with principle 7 of Brummitt & Powell's *Authors of Plant Names* (1992: 10), the preferable author abbreviation is probably 'F.Berge'.

Etymology of *Cereaster*—It is unclear whether, and if so how, the generic name *Cereaster* is derived from the earlier name *Cereus* sect. *Creastris* DC. The two names are essentially identical, *Creastris* being the plural of *Cereaster*, and both pertain to the genus *Cereus* (the first as an offsplit, the second as a subdivision), but they were used in an almost opposite sense. While Berge evidently established *Cereaster* to contain the *Cereus* species that lacked the upright habit typical for this genus, de Candolle included in his *Creastris* 'the real Cerei' ['les vrais Cierges ou les Céréastes'], characterized by a stem that was 'dressée, ferme, et n'étant ni articulée, ni grimpante, ni étalée' ['erect, firm and neither articulated, nor climbing, nor sprawling'] (de Candolle père 1828: 40). Berge's *Cereaster* roughly corresponds to de Candolle's *Cereus* sect. *Serpentini*, whose name he explained as an allusion to *Cereus serpentinus* DC. and to *Cereus flagelliformis* Mill., 'qui les jardiniers appellent *Cierge serpent*' ['which the gardeners call *Snake Cereus*'] (l. c.: 48).

If Berge coined the name *Cereaster* independently from de Candolle, the similarity in names is a striking coincidence. If he did know about it, which seems likely, as it was accepted by most contemporary authors, he may have changed the application of the name for etymological reasons. He apparently interpreted

³ Scathing reviews by Finckh (1832: [ii-iii]) and Reider (1834: vii-viii).

Cereastri as a compound of *Cereus* and *-aster* or *-astrum*, a suffix denoting an incomplete resemblance (i.e. ‘semi-*Cereus*’) (Rybolt 1971). Confusingly, *-astrum* was also used in the opposite sense to form the name of ‘la principale division d’un genre’, as de Candolle fils (1867: 21) recommended in Art. 29.1 of the *Lois de la nomenclature botanique*. It seems, therefore, that the name *Cereastri* (sensu de Candolle) was meant to convey that it contained the type of the genus *Cereus*, while the name *Cereaster* (sensu Berge) was meant to convey that it did *not*.

Cereaster was mentioned by several contemporary authors, though almost exclusively more or less in the sense of de Candolle.⁴ Labouret (1853: 273-275) proposed a genus named *Cereastreæ* (arguably correctable to *Cereaster* under ICN Art. 32.2⁵), which included the subgenera *Pilocereus* (Lem.) Labour., *Echinopsis* (Zucc.) Labour. and *Cereus* (Haw.) Labour.

Berge’s German designations for *Cereus* and *Cereaster* were *Fackeldistel* ‘torch-thistle’ and *Schlangendistel* ‘snake-thistle’. These names had already been used with essentially the same application by Krausse (1783: 51), e.g. *Cactus grandiflorus* = *großblümigte Schlangen=Distel* ‘large-flowered snake-thistle’ (Berge: *großblumige Schlangendistel*), *Cactus flagelliformis* = *rankenförmige Schlangen=Distel* ‘vine-like snake-thistle’ (Berge: *peitschenförmige Schlangendistel* ‘whip-like snake-thistle’). *Schlangenkaktus* ‘snake-cactus’ is still the usual common name for *Aporocactus flagelliformis* and is sometimes used for *Selenicereus* as well.

Etymology of *Terecaulis*—This generic name is an incorrectly formed compound of Latin *teres*, *teretis* ‘terete’ and *caulis* ‘stem’. The correct formation would be *Tereticaulis*. It does not seem to be based on any previous taxon name. The only pre-1842 occurrence of this word in any taxon name is in *Euphorbia terecaulis* = *Euphorbia tirucalli* L. In this epithet, *terecaulis* is apparently a

⁴ E.g. *Cereaster* DC. = *Cactus* L. (Reichenbach 1837: 234), *Cereaster* DC. = *Cereus* Haw. (Wittstein: 1856: 177), *Cactus* [unranked] *Cereaster* DC. = *Cactus* [unranked] *Cereus* Juss. (Reichenbach 1828: 160), *Cactus* [unranked] *Cereaster* (Heß 1846: 462), *Cereus* sect. *Eucereus* subsect. *Cereaster* (Todaro 1857/1858: 739).

⁵ Labouret demoted Salm-Dyck’s tribes to the rank of genus, but, with the exception of *Athrophyllum* (= tribe Phyllocactaeae), did not change their names accordingly: *Melocactææ*, *Echinocactææ*, *Cereastreææ* (from which he split off *Leuchtenbergiææ* as a separate genus), *Rhipsalidææ*, *Opuntieææ* and *Peiresciææ*. Since generic names must be in singular form (ICN Art. 20.1) and the suffix *-eae* denotes a tribe (ICN Art. 19.3), these names are correctable to *Melocactus*, *Echinocactus*, *Cereaster*, *Rhipsalis*, *Opuntia* and *Peirescia* (*Pereskia*) rather than *Melocactææ*, *Echinocactææ*, *Cereastreææ*, *Rhipsalidææ*, *Opuntieææ* and *Peiresciææ*.

folk-etymological corruption of the unrelated Malayalam vernacular name *tirukali* ‘good spurge’.

Berge divided the *Feigencacten* ‘fig-cacti’ into the genera *Scheibendistel* ‘disk-thistle’ (*Opuntia*) and *Afterfcheibendistel* ‘false disk-thistle’ (*Terecaulis*). This is the earliest known attestation of the word *Scheibendistel*. (*Scheibencactus* was used by Förster (1846) for *Discocactus* Pfeiff.) See Adelung (1793: 175) for the now-obsolete use of the prefix *after-* to indicate that something ‘einem andern Dinge ähnlich ist, aber sich doch noch merklich von demselben unterscheidet’ [‘is similar to another thing, but still noticeably differs from it’]; in modern German, *After* means ‘anus’.

Species included in *Cereaster*—Berge initially included nine taxa in *Cereaster* (marked with * in the table below) and added six more in 1843, when he divided the genus in two nameless *Abtheilungen*. Only *C. grandiflorus*, *C. flagelliformis*, *C. serpentinus* and *C. setaceus* are described. No basionyms are cited, but since the context makes it clear that all species were previously included in *Cereus*, in several cases the mere mention of the specific epithet qualifies as an unambiguous indirect basionym reference under ICN Artt. 38.14 and 41.3. These combinations must be considered validly published.⁶

ABTHEILUNG 1:
1. <i>Cereaster flagelliformis</i> (<i>peitfchenförmige Schlangendistel</i>) *
≡ <i>Cactus flagelliformis</i> L.
≡ <i>Cereus flagelliformis</i> (L.) Mill.
≡ <i>Aporocactus flagelliformis</i> (L.) Lem. [type]
2. <i>Cereaster flagriformis</i> (–)
≡ <i>Cereus flagriformis</i> Pfeiff.
= <i>Aporocactus flagelliformis</i> (L.) Lem. [type]
3. <i>Cereaster martianus</i> (–)
≡ <i>Cereus martianus</i> Zucc. ex Pfeiff.
≡ <i>Aporocactus martianus</i> (Zucc. ex Pfeiff.) Britton & Rose

⁶ It is not my intention to validate any names here.

4. *Cereaster serpentinus* (weichstachelige Schlangendistel) *
≡ *Cactus serpentinus* Lag. & Rodr.
≡ *Cereus serpentinus* (Lag. & Rodr.) DC.
≡ *Nyctocereus serpentinus* (Lag. & Rodr.) Britton & Rose [type]

ABTHEILUNG 2:

5. *Cereaster grandiflorus* (großblumige Schlangendistel) *
≡ *Cactus grandiflorus* L.
≡ *Cereus grandiflorus* (L.) Mill.
≡ *Selenicereus grandiflorus* (L.) Britton & Rose [type]

6. *Cereaster reptans* (kletternde Schlangendistel) *

7. *Cereaster caripensis* (–)
≡ *Cactus caripensis* Kunth
≡ *Cereus caripensis* (Kunth) DC.
= *Rhipsalis cassytha* Gaertn. [type]
= *Rhipsalis baccifera* (J.S.Muell.) Stearn

8. *Cereaster serpens* (–)
≡ *Cactus serpens* Kunth
≡ *Cereus serpens* (Kunth) DC.
≡ *Cleistocactus serpens* (Kunth) A.Weber

9. *Cereaster extensus* (ausgebreiteter Schlangendistel) *
≡ *Cereus extensus* Salm-Dyck ex DC.
≡ *Selenicereus extensus* (Salm-Dyck ex DC.) Leuenb.

10. *Cereaster prismaticus* (–)

11. *Cereaster triqueter* (–) *

12. *Cereaster triangularis* (dreieckige Schlangendistel) *

13. *Cereaster triangularis variegatus* (fchäckige Schlangendistel) *

14. *Cereaster bonplandii* (bonplandifche Schlangendistel) *

15. *Cereaster setaceus* (–)
≡ *Cereus setaceus* Salm-Dyck ex DC.
≡ *Selenicereus setaceus* (Salm-Dyck ex DC.) A.Berger ex Werderm.

Species included in *Terecaulis*—The five species included in this genus were all previously assigned to *Opuntia*.

1. *Terecaulis curassavicus* (*kuraffavische Afterfcheibendistel*) *
≡ *Cactus curassavicus* L.
≡ *Opuntia curassavica* (L.) Mill.
2. *Terecaulis foliosus* (*blättrige Afterfcheibendistel*) *
≡ *Cactus foliosus* Willd.
≡ *Opuntia foliosa* (Willd.) Salm-Dyck ex DC.
= *Opuntia pusilla* (Haw.) Haw.
3. *Terecaulis fragilis* (*zerbrechliche Afterfcheibendistel*) *
≡ *Cactus fragilis* Nutt.
≡ *Opuntia fragilis* (Nutt.) Haw.
4. *Terecaulis nanus* (*niedrige Afterfcheibendistel*) *
≡ *Cactus opuntia* var. *nana* DC.
≡ *Opuntia nana* (DC.) Steudel
5. *Terecaulis horizontalis* (–) *
≡ *Opuntia horizontalis* Gillies ex Pfeiff.
= *Cylindropuntia imbricata* (Haw.) F.M.Knuth

Typification—No types were designated. Mottram dealt with *Terecaulis* by designating *Cactus curassavicus* as the lectotype, rendering the genus a subjective synonym of *Opuntia*. It is not possible to remove *Cereaster* from contention with later names this way, since it has priority over *Aporocactus* Lem., *Nyctocereus* (Berger) Britton & Rose and *Selenicereus* (Berger) Britton & Rose, the three genera

the species mentioned in the original publication are currently assigned to.⁷ This name may require formal rejection.

Terecaulis horizontalis (1842)

Cereaster grandiflorus (1842)

⁷ Under ICN Art. 7.9 the type is to be 'selected from the context of its valid publication', which precludes consideration of the species added in 1843.

Cereaster setaceus (1843)

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